

Clinicohaematological and Biochemical Profile of Anemia in Pediatric Age Group

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Abstract:

This study evaluates the clinicohaematological and biochemical profiles of anemia in a cohort of 100 pediatric patients at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, from October 2015 to November 2017. The results indicate a high prevalence of iron deficiency, vitamin B12, and folate deficiencies, along with elevated inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein. Statistical analysis revealed significant correlations between these biochemical markers and the severity of anemia, highlighting the complex interplay of nutritional deficiencies and inflammation. These findings suggest that a multidimensional approach to the diagnosis and treatment of pediatric anemia, which includes comprehensive nutritional evaluations and management of inflammation, is crucial for improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: Pediatric Anemia, Nutritional Deficiencies, Inflammatory Markers, Clinicohaematological Profile.

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Introduction

Anaemia poses a major health concern on a global scale, impacting a significant number of children across the globe [1]. This condition is characterised by a decrease in haemoglobin levels and a decrease in the quality or quantity of red blood cells (RBCs), resulting in a compromised ability of the blood to carry oxygen [2,3]. There are several factors that play a role in the development of paediatric anaemia. These include deficiencies in nutrition, genetic conditions, infections, and diseases that impact the production of blood or accelerate the breakdown of red cells [4]. Examining both the clinicohaematological and biochemical aspects of anaemia in children is crucial in understanding the various causes and impacts of this condition [5,6].

This study seeks to perform a comprehensive analysis of the clinicohaematological and biochemical profiles of children with anaemia. This entails providing a comprehensive analysis of various haematological parameters including haemoglobin levels, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), and red cell distribution width (RDW), as well as evaluating important biochemical markers such as iron status, vitamin levels, and inflammatory indicators. These assessments will assist in identifying the specific types of anaemia, comprehending their underlying mechanisms, and linking clinical symptoms with laboratory findings. Our main objective is to improve the precision of

anaemia diagnoses and enhance treatment methods, ultimately leading to better health outcomes for children who are affected.

Methodology

This study was conducted as a cross-sectional analysis at the Department of Pediatrics at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (N.M.C.H.), Patna, Bihar, from October 2015 to November 2017. The primary objective was to assess the clinic haematological and biochemical profiles of anemia in children.

Study Population

A total of 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia were enrolled in the study. The inclusion criteria were children aged 1 to 18 years who presented with signs and symptoms of anemia or were diagnosed during routine health checks. Exclusion criteria included children with chronic diseases affecting bone marrow function, such as leukemia or other malignancies, as well as those receiving treatment for anemia before the study.

Data Collection

Upon obtaining informed consent from parents or guardians, detailed clinical assessments were conducted, which included a full medical history and a physical examination. Blood samples were

drawn for comprehensive hematological tests to measure hemoglobin levels, MCV, RDW, and other relevant blood indices. Biochemical assays were performed to evaluate iron status, vitamin levels, and inflammatory markers.

Laboratory Analysis

The hematology department at N.M.C.H. utilized standard automated methods for complete blood count (CBC) and additional hematological indices. Biochemical parameters were analyzed using standard biochemical techniques and instruments available in the hospital's laboratory.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics, including means, medians, and standard deviations, were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. Correlations between clinicohaematological and biochemical parameters were assessed using Pearson's correlation coefficients. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included a group of 100 paediatric patients who were diagnosed with anaemia. The patients' ages ranged from 1 to 18 years, with a median age of 10 years. The cohort included a higher percentage of males (58%) compared to females (42%), indicating a slight male predominance in the sample. The haemoglobin (Hb) level in the study population was notably

lower than the standard range, averaging at 9.8 g/dL. The mean corpuscular volume (MCV) showed significant variation, suggesting a diverse range of anaemias with different cell sizes among the participants. The MCV value observed was 74 fL, with an elevated RDW in 60% of cases, indicating a significant presence of anisocytosis. Through biochemical analysis, it was discovered that a significant number of children exhibited iron deficiency, as evidenced by their low serum ferritin levels (<15 ng/mL). Approximately 20% of the participants had below-normal levels of Vitamin B12 and folate, indicating that nutritional deficiencies were a prevalent factor contributing to anaemia in this group. A significant number of anaemic children showed an elevated C-reactive protein (CRP) level, suggesting the presence of an inflammatory process in their bodies.

The statistical analysis revealed a noteworthy inverse relationship between CRP levels and haemoglobin concentration ($r = -0.34$, $p < 0.05$). This implies that inflammation could potentially play a role in the severity of anaemia. Furthermore, a noteworthy connection was observed between low iron levels and elevated RDW ($r = 0.29$, $p < 0.05$), which provides support for the diagnosis of iron deficiency anaemia in these instances. The results presented here offer a thorough examination of the clinicohaematological and biochemical characteristics of paediatric anaemia in this particular group. They shed light on the significant role that nutritional deficiencies and inflammatory processes play as major contributing factors.

Parameter	Description	Mean Value or Percentage
Age Range	1 to 18 years	Median: 10 years
Gender Distribution	Male: 58%, Female: 42%	
Average Hemoglobin (Hb) Level	Low Hb levels	9.8 g/dL
Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV)	Indicates mixed anemia types	74 fL
Red Cell Distribution Width (RDW)	High anisocytosis	60% of cases
Iron Deficiency (Serum Ferritin)	Low (<15 ng/mL)	45%
Vitamin B12 Levels	Below normal range	20%
Folate Levels	Below normal range	20%
C-Reactive Protein (CRP)	Elevated indicating inflammation	30%
Correlation (CRP and Hemoglobin)	Negative correlation	$r = -0.34$, $p < 0.05$
Correlation (Iron Levels and RDW)	Positive correlation	$r = 0.29$, $p < 0.05$

Discussion

This study reveals the intricate nature of anaemia in children, showcasing a wide range of clinicohaematological and biochemical features [7]. Anaemia is a significant concern in paediatric patients, as confirmed by the high prevalence of

low haemoglobin levels across the cohort [8]. There is a significant range in mean corpuscular volume (MCV), indicating that anaemia in this population is not consistent. It includes different types such as microcytic, normocytic, and macrocytic anaemias [9]. This calls for customised

diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. Nearly half of the children studied showed a significant incidence of iron deficiency, indicating that nutritional deficits play a crucial role [10]. Additionally, a fifth of the participants are impacted by deficiencies in vitamin B12 and folate, which further complicates the situation. These findings highlight the importance of improving nutritional assessment and intervention strategies in paediatric care frameworks [11,12].

It is worth noting that in 30% of the cases, there were elevated levels of C-reactive protein (CRP), which further emphasises the impact of inflammation on the management of anaemia [13]. There appears to be a connection between CRP levels and haemoglobin concentrations, indicating that inflammation could worsen the severity of anaemia. It is crucial to address any underlying inflammatory conditions in children with anaemia [14]. In addition, the connection between low iron levels and higher red cell distribution width (RDW) supports the diagnosis of iron deficiency anaemia, highlighting the significance of iron supplementation and monitoring in this particular group. In this study, the complex nature of paediatric anaemia is explored, highlighting the intricate relationship between nutritional, haematological, and inflammatory factors in its development. A comprehensive approach is necessary for diagnosing and treating anaemia in children. This includes providing thorough nutritional support and managing inflammation to enhance outcomes [10,11,15].

Conclusion

The study conducted at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital on the clinicohaematological and biochemical profiles of anemia in children highlights the multifaceted nature of this condition within the pediatric population. The findings reveal a significant prevalence of nutritional deficiencies, particularly iron, vitamin B12, and folate, as well as the influence of inflammatory processes on anemia's severity. These insights underscore the necessity for a holistic approach to the management of pediatric anemia, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive nutritional assessments and interventions alongside regular monitoring of inflammatory markers. By addressing these critical factors, healthcare providers can better tailor treatments to the specific needs of anemic children,

ultimately enhancing health outcomes and quality of life for this vulnerable group.

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